

FROM ACRAALITY IN THE FORMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND ART IN THE ERA OF CULTURE OF MEDIEVAL UZBEKISTAN

Nazarova Malika

second-year master's student of TASU,

M.R. Borodina

Caf. "Interior and landscape design"

Supervisor: Professor

Annotation. The article is devoted to the concept of "cultural context" and the consideration of cultural objects as a result of the laws of comprehension of being. Belonging to the semantic space of Islamic culture, unites the personality with its history and determines the intellect and development. Culture is defined as a space of meanings, i.e. a "man-made environment", a world in which a person "objectifies" into himself, his understanding of the world.

Key words: Islamic culture, sacredness, architecture, Koran, art, science.

A deep study of the Holy Scriptures, its hidden meaning, the size of ayats (verses), sounds, words and rhymes has a spiritual impact on Islamic art, including sacred architecture.

The first principle of Islam is the principle of the unity and uniqueness of God – tawhid. This principle allows the use of the language of diversity by means of architecture and art. To convey this principle, architecture and art create a kind of sacred abstract space, fundamentally different from the modern interior. The abstract thinking and art of Islam directly reflects unity in diversity, based on the Qur'an. The Islamic Holy Scripture states that the world is created wisely, as an integral harmony. It contains geometric shapes that underlie the diversity of the world.

In Islam, the universal principle of creating an art form was developed. A significant role is given to sacred geometry. **Sacred geometry is the study of the forms of space and their laws.** Sacred geometry connects the material aspects with their spiritual essence. This science embodies the interaction of the visible and the **invisible, the manifested and the unmanifested, the finite and the infinite.**

For example: a mosque personifies a world where everything is strictly marked and **logically constructed.**

It must be said that the mathematical nature of Islamic philosophy did not arise from external historical influences, but from the philosophy of the Qur'an. **Its mathematical structure** reveals the connection between the intellectual and spiritual interests of Islam and mathematics.

In a sense, the **mathematical nature of Islamic art is the outward expression** of the mathematics hidden in the very structure of the Qur'an and the numerical symbolism of its letters and words.

For the artistic method of conveying this order on earth, **sacred geometry is used.** The original forms of the geometric sacralization of the universe are represented by a sphere, a square, a circle, a **triangle, a rectangle and their combinations.**

Islamic philosophy says that without knowledge of geometry and harmony it is impossible to create sacred forms and art, since this knowledge is the key to the mysteries of the universe.

Sacred geometry is a combination of shape and number.

From this it follows that in religious Islamic architecture, the presence of God can be revealed in certain patterns of forms, determined by numerical proportions and ratios, as well as **degrees of angle.** Directly through number and form, and not through artistic images, the greatness of the Almighty is manifested.

Based on this, the divine presence is achieved in works of art, where number and form are at the core, that is, through architecture. But not through pictorial decorations

or images. "Sacred numbers" in Islam, as in other religions, have their own qualitative dimension and symbolize certain meanings.

Here are some examples. **The number "two" symbolizes the spirit, "four" - integrity, totality, completeness (four cardinal points, seasons, sides of the square).**

The number "four" and its geometrical equivalent, the square, **denote God (the square altar)** and the material world created by him. The Islamic quaternary includes the **principle of four components (creator, world spirit, world soul, primordial matter).**

The number "five" symbolizes the five **pillars of Islam** (faith, prayer, pilgrimage, fasting, mercy), the five divine presences, and the fivefold daily prayer.

The number "seven" in Islam, as in Christianity and Judaism, symbolizes the seven **stages of the creation of the universe**. In Islam, the "seven" has a special meaning. The number "seven" symbolizes the seven heavens, the seven prophets, the seventh heaven (the highest bliss). Pilgrims go around the Holy Kaaba seven times.

The number "eight" in Islam symbolizes the throne, which is supported by eight angels, corresponding to the eight directions and eight groups of letters of the Arabic alphabet. Eight as the **first cubic number embodies the Earth, its volume, three-dimensionality, perfection of the six faces of the cube.**

This mathematical symbol is eight winds and cardinal points - four main and four intermediate (southeast, southwest, northeast, northwest). The octagon formed is a "wind rose" called "eight winds". In graphic form, this symbolism is indicated by an octahedron and the imposition of a straight line and standing at the corner of the squares.

Consider the semiotic reading of numbers on examples of geometric shapes. **The square is the basic form, receptacle and basis of the manifested world. "Four" is a symbol of peace, spreading in four directions. The square is a symbol of the orderliness of the universe.** The structure of the square characterizes the spatial

composition of the universe (cardinal points, wind direction), temporal coordinates (four parts of the day, four seasons).

The dome is a hemispherical shape, which, thanks to its soft and smooth bend, is directed upwards, which also has a **semiotic reading**. One of the foreign researchers associates the curvature of the dome with **the humility and obedience of Muslims**. He writes: "The vaulted and arched form in Islamic architecture is endowed with a deep and special meaning. This form, which can be seen in some elements of the mosque, such as the dome, symbolizes a valuable state of mind for a person and demonstrates humility and humility.

In the Qur'an, there is often a mention of the invisible and visible world, where the invisible world is identified with the spiritual, and the visible with the bodily or material.¹

The emptiness of the interior symbolizes spiritual freedom and a sense of the presence of the Spirit, emphasized in Islamic revelation. The combination of these factors gives the emptiness of the interior space of Islamic architecture a spiritual meaning of great importance. In the works of Muslim thinkers Al-Farabi (872-950) and Al-Biruni (973-1050), the reason for the fundamental two-dimensionality of the interpretation of space in Islamic art is explained.

The architecture in the landscape of a Muslim city is expressive precisely because of its silhouette. In this regard, the perception and **comprehension of sacred architecture (three-dimensional, three-dimensional) go beyond the limits of three-dimensional space**. This approach leaves an opportunity for a person to rise above the material vision and creates a field for spiritual understanding of sacred architecture and the expansion of spiritual knowledge, since the **"two" symbolizes the spirit**.

¹ Shukurov Sh.M. Image of the temple. Moscow: Progress-Traditsiya, 2002. 496 p. (in Russian).

Consequently, the **sacred space, organized by an architectural structure, becomes a symbolic model of the world order**. Its understanding is given to a person not in specific sensations or images, but speculatively, that is, through penetration into the spiritual essence of architecture and art. Beauty becomes not only an aesthetic given, but also the basis of understanding the Truth, penetration into the inner (spiritual) meaning of the contemplated.

A semiotic reading of the cultural context **of sacred Islamic architecture reveals its inner (spiritual) dimension and cultural features**.

Islamic sacred art is closely related to the Quran and aims to convey the external and internal beauty of the Holy Quran in artistic architectural forms. The architectural forms of sacred Islamic architecture, without imitating the external forms of nature, reflect the principles and concepts of Islam.

Sacred architecture becomes the outward expression of mathematics, hidden in the structure of the Qur'an and the numerical symbolism of its letters and words. Architecture shapes, organizes and orients space using various technical and artistic techniques.

In Islam, the material world cannot serve as a source of inspiration for the artist, an ideal of beauty, "for everything earthly is unstable, changeable, illusory, transient" - as it is said in the Qur'an. **Sacred art is based on the science of the inner nature and spiritual essence of the depicted object**.

Islamic sacred architecture sets the task not to imitate the external forms of nature, but to select their concepts and principles.

A significant role here is given **to sacred geometry as a synthesis of form and number**. The mathematical nature of Islamic sacred architecture is not based on historical traditions, it goes back to the Koran.

Reference literature

1. Bulatov M.S. Geometric harmonization in the architecture of Central Asia of the IX-XV centuries. Moscow: Nauka, 1978. 380 p. (in Russian)
2. Shukurov Sh.M. Image of the temple. Moscow: Progress-Traditsiya, 2002. 496 p. (in Russian).